

Original Research Report

Perceived Entrepreneurial Sustainability and Financial Stability Among Fashion Designers in Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This research explore factors influencing entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability within the context of the fashion industry, with a focus on the perceptions of fashion designers in Abia State. Descriptive survey methods were employed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. The total population for the study was 487, which comprises all registered fashion designers operating in Aba, hence the whole population was used for the study. The study was carried out in Aba which is one of the major fashion hubs in Abia State. Data was collected through structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Perceived Entrepreneurial Sustainability and Financial Stability among Fashion Designers (QPESFAFD). The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the items on each objective. The findings revealed that there are perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers, and perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses. It also revealed that there are challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability. Based on the findings, recommendations were made that, there should be regular workshops and training sessions that will focus on financial management and planning specifically tailored for fashion designers and networking and collaboration platforms should facilitate knowledge sharing, resource pooling, and collaboration among fashion designers in Abia State

Keywords: Abia State, Fashion Designers, Financial Stability, Perceived Entrepreneurial

1. Introduction

Fashion designers are the creative minds behind the garments and accessories that shape our sense of style and identity. They improve the fashion industry in blending artistry, innovation, and market awareness to create clothing that captivates and inspires. A variety of sources, including art, culture, history, and current trends, serve as inspiration for fashion designers (Arnold, 2009; Peirson-Smith, & Peirson-Smith, 2020). They do out research to provide insight into their design ideas and create a distinct visual identity. In order to transform their vision into concrete designs, designers use their artistic abilities to sketch out their ideas and experiment with colors, materials, and shapes (Manovich, 2021; Xenakis, & Arnellos, 2023). To get the desired appearance and feel of a garment, selecting the appropriate fabrics and materials is essential. Consequently, in order to choose premium materials that complement their design concept, designers collaborate closely with fabric providers. Also, designers create patterns and prototypes to bring their designs to life. The fashion industry is highly competitive, with countless designers vying for attention and recognition. Standing out in a crowded market requires originality, innovation, and a distinct design aesthetic. Fashion trends change quickly, and designers find it difficult to adapt to shifting customer tastes (Johnson, 2023; Yang, 2020). So, in order to stay ahead of the curve, designers need to constantly innovate and adjust to new trends. It may be difficult to strike a balance between creativity and pragmatism, especially when it comes to production limitations like cost, time, and scalability. To guarantee that their ideas are viable for mass production, designers must carefully combine their creative vision with financial feasibility (Sánchez, & Hartlieb, 2020; Yulistiyono, Andriani, & Rukmana, 2023). The fashion industry is under increasing pressure to adopt sustainable methods as a result of increased public awareness of environmental and social concerns. Aakko and Niinimäki (2018) delineate the types of obstacles that fashion designers have when juggling their dual responsibilities as designers and entrepreneurs, as well as the possible benefits of such job. The findings demonstrate that in order to manage their businesses, fashion designers who are also entrepreneurs need to possess advanced managerial abilities. Maintaining a healthy balance between personal and professional life is another essential component of success. Additionally, the research indicates that rather than a dearth of investors, the barrier to business expansion may be the designer's business mindset. As a result, it's critical to understand the many forces that affect the industry, appreciate intrinsic characteristics (such as artistic and creative qualities), and let these influences influence the industry.

Despite these challenges, the fashion industry also presents numerous opportunities for growth and innovation. The opportunities for growth and innovation are being created by technological advancements, changing consumer preferences, and changing market dynamics (Dahmani, Benhida, Belhadi, Kamble, Elfezazi, & Jauhar, 2021; Singh, Chirade, Taluja, R., Yadav, Srikanth, Manjunatha, & Karim, 2023; Okogwu, Agho, Adeyinka, Odulaja, Eyo-UdoDaraojimba, & Banso, 2023). In an industry that is always changing, designers that embrace change, take use of new technology, and put sustainability first will stand to prosper. By analyzing this link and Brisbane's low ranking on the hierarchy of fashion cities, they argue that the idea of a fashion city itself is illusive and that other than traditional fashion centers, all other cities are constantly changing. Fashion practice was

paradigmatically shaped by the First, Second, Third, and now, the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Bertola & Teunissen, 2018).

Fashion 4.0 is a term used to describe a new organizational and technological paradigm that is loosely associated with Industry 4.0. It operates in the cyber-physical space and progresses toward smart products, automation, optimization, and flexibility as well as processes that are data-fied, customer-driven, and sustainability-oriented (Bertola & Teunissen, 2018). Fashion 4.0 may be seen in the broader framework of a postindustrial network society, in which individuals are less bound by space and time and value experiences over material possessions (Castells, 2010). According to Hunt's (2005) Manifesto for Postindustrial Design, authoritative, centrally positioned designers are going extinct along with heavy mechanized mass manufacturing. Thus, these studies identify micro-size fashion companies as businesses where sustainability is a successful means of living with a combination of fashion creativity and entrepreneurial sustainability.

Entrepreneurial sustainability refers to the capacity of entrepreneurs and their ventures to create long-term economic, social, and environmental value while maintaining profitability and competitiveness. It may also be described as an entrepreneurial activity when the creation and exchange of commodities and services serves as a means of achieving various non-economic and economic objectives as an intermediary or instrumental goal (Civitillo, 2023). By combining social responsibility, environmental stewardship, and economic viability, it represents the concepts of sustainable development (Almagtome, Khaghaany, & Önce, 2020). As a result, entrepreneurial sustainability has attracted a lot of attention lately as companies realize how crucial it is to strike a balance between their need to maximize profits and more general societal and environmental objectives. However, according to Fischer, Brettel, & Mauer, 2020; Kamaludin, Xavier, & Amin, 2024, there are other dimensions of entrepreneurial sustainability. These include economic sustainability, which is defined as the long-term financial stability and consistent profit-making potential of company activities. The phrase "social sustainability" describes how entrepreneurial endeavors benefit society as a whole, including the welfare of stakeholders like as communities and employees. It also refers to the necessity of efficient operations, good resource management, and the ability to adapt to shifting customer preferences and market dynamics. According to research, fashion designers' perceptions about their abilities to continue their businesses have a beneficial impact on their financial stability. Research conducted by Olokundun et al. (2018) and Okpara and Wynn (2007) revealed that fashion designers that put sustainable practices first typically have stronger financial results and are more resilient in volatile market conditions.

In addition to encouraging social justice, inclusive growth, and community development, environmental sustainability aims to reduce the negative effects of entrepreneurship on the environment and promote resource conservation and responsible usage. Finally, it entails embracing renewable energy sources, cutting carbon emissions, and implementing eco-friendly behaviors. But, entrepreneurial sustainability is being recognized more and more as a source of fortitude and a competitive edge in the market. Because the world is now digital, fashion designers need to go beyond just remaining in the shop and be creative and original in what they do. Businesses which embrace

sustainability are more likely to attract talent, investors, and customers who respect ethics and accountability (Isabel, Teixeira, Luis, & Silva, 2023; Ahsan, 2024). Diverse factors, including education, experience, and cultural background, influence how fashion designers see sustainability (Goworek et al., 2012). While some designers place a premium on environmentally responsible materials and production methods, others pay more attention to moral hiring procedures and community involvement (Okogwu, Agho, Adeyinka, Odulaja, Eyo-Udo, Daraojimba, & Banso, 2023; Khan, Jhariya, Raj, Banerjee, & Meena, 2021). Integrating social and environmental concerns into company operations is a key component of sustainable entrepreneurship (Lans, Blok, & Wesselink, 2014; Belz, & Binder, 2017). According to Bianchi et al. (2015), perceived obstacles to sustainability include lack of knowledge, limited market demand, and cost concerns.

Even with the growing awareness of entrepreneurial sustainability, fashion enterprises still have challenges adopting sustainable practices due to institutional barriers, market pressures, and cost constraints. However, these challenges also present opportunities for originality, collaboration, and market distinctiveness. The concept of entrepreneurial sustainability is therefore multifaceted, encompassing aspects of business operations and strategy related to social, economic, and environmental domains (Rizos, Behrens, Van der Gaast, Hofman, Ioannou, Kafyeke, & Topi, 2016; Gast, Gundolf, & Cesinger, 2017). Entrepreneurs may promote economic success and the welfare of the environment and society by using sustainable practices. As sustainability continues to gain prominence in the global business landscape, entrepreneurs will shape a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable future to financial stability.

Financial stability refers to the ability of an individual, organization, or economy to withstand economic shocks and uncertainties while maintaining sustainable financial health and resilience (Rizos, Behrens, Van der Gaast, Hofman, Ioannou, Kafyeke, & Topi, 2016). Within the fashion design industry, financial stability pertains to a company's capacity to sustain sound financial standing, fulfill financial commitments, efficiently handle cash flow, and weather economic ups and downs without experiencing major disturbances. In order to ensure that an organization can satisfy its financial commitments when they become due without experiencing insolvency or major interruptions to its operations, financial stability also entails maintaining a balance between assets and liabilities (Gast, Gundolf, & Cesinger, 2017). It includes a number of elements, such as risk management, profitability, liquidity, and solvency. Long-term success and prosperity for people, companies, financial institutions, and whole economies depend on achieving and preserving financial stability (Miles, Feulner, & Mary Anastasia O'Grady, 2004; Rowe, 2001; Hajian, & Kashani, 2021). Several studies have explored the factors influencing financial stability among fashion designers. In their paper "Challenges of Fashion Designing Business in Aba Metropolis," for instance, Okeke and Ogujiuba (2019) emphasized problems like infrastructural limitations, market demand, and financing accessibility. Anyanwu et al. (2020) conducted a research titled "Entrepreneurial Skills and Financial Management Practices among Fashion Designers in Abia State," which emphasized the significance of cost management and financial literacy for the success of businesses.

Long-term expansion, reinvestment, and the capacity to resist market unfavorable conditions and economic downturns all depend on sustainable profitability (Sultan, 2014; Buljat, Covic, & Galic, 2020). Risk management: Stability of finances depends on effective risk management. This entails determining, evaluating, and reducing a variety of risks, including as liquidity, credit, market, and operational risks. Adopting strong risk management procedures improves resilience to external shocks and protects against unforeseen losses (Ruozi, Ferrari, Ruozi, & Ferrari, 2013; Wanjohi, 2013; Aloqab, Alobaidi, & Raweh, 2018). Adherence to Regulations: Maintaining financial stability requires adherence to regulatory rules and procedures, especially for financial institutions. Respecting regulatory frameworks lowers the possibility of financial crises and systemic risks by fostering good governance, accountability, and transparency (Castellano & Dubovec, 2017; Claessens & Rojas-Suarez, 2016; Anarfo & Abor, 2020). Therefore, for a number of reasons, financial stability is essential for people, businesses, and economies. Investment, entrepreneurship, and innovation are stimulated by financial stability, which builds confidence and trust in the financial system. The effective deployment of capital is made possible by stable financial markets, which promote long-term economic growth and development. Investors, depositors, and other stakeholders are more confident when there is financial stability, which draws capital inflows and facilitates easy access to loans on advantageous conditions. Liquidity, stability, and the smooth operation of markets depend on public confidence in the integrity and stability of financial institutions.

Fashion design is a thriving and dynamic industry that shapes consumer tastes, cultural trends, and economic growth via creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Fashion entrepreneurship has the potential to be successful, but it also presents a number of obstacles, including resource scarcity, market saturation, shifting customer preferences, and financial limits. However, many fashion designers in Abia state struggle to maintain their enterprises and achieve financial stability despite their creative abilities and entrepreneurial initiatives. The fashion sector in Abia State is well known for producing traditional textiles, like as the well-known "Aba-made" textiles (Anyaehe & Anyanwu, 2020). Access to sustainable materials, infrastructure, access to funding and capital, maintaining a loyal customer, lack of infrastructure and resources, high operational costs, maintaining strong brand identity and governmental regulations and policies, and market prospects are among the hurdles that local fashion designers in Abia State must overcome (Ihejirika & Ndu, 2018). Therefore, in order to increase their competitiveness and satisfy customer demand, Abia State fashion designers are becoming more interested in using sustainable methods (Okechukwu & Okafor, 2019). The problem of the study lies in the gap between the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies of fashion designers and their actual financial stability. While some designers may perceive themselves as adopting sustainable practices and innovative approaches to business, the reality may differ due to various external factors such as market competition, consumer preferences, resource constraints, and economic volatility. This research will contribute to the understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by fashion entrepreneurs in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability in a dynamic and competitive industry. It will shed light on the strategies and practices employed by entrepreneurs to sustain their businesses in a competitive market environment. It will also

provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by fashion entrepreneurs in achieving financial stability and long-term success.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Financial stability is essential for people, businesses, and economies. Investment, entrepreneurship, and innovation are stimulated by financial stability, which builds confidence and trust in the financial system. Thus Perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability are critical aspects of business success, particularly among fashion designers in Abia State. The dynamic nature of the fashion industry, coupled with the unique economic challenges in Nigeria, necessitates a closer examination of these issues. Abia State, like many regions in Nigeria, faces economic instability characterized by fluctuating economic policies, inflation, limited access to capital, and limited access to financial resources. These challenges create a volatile environment for entrepreneurs, making it difficult to sustain businesses over the long term and also makes many fashion designers struggle to obtain the necessary funds to start or expand their businesses. Furthermore, entrepreneurial success in the fashion industry requires more than just creative talent; it also demands business acumen, marketing skills, and technical expertise. However, many fashion designers in Abia State lack access to comprehensive training and education programs that can equip them with these necessary skills. Hence this study wish identify perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability among fashion designers in Abia state

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to identify perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability among fashion designers in Abia state. Specific purpose is to:

- (a) understand the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State
- (b) identify the perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region
- (c) highlight the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State?
- (b) How do these perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region?
- (c) What are the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design to investigate perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability among fashion designers in Abia State. A descriptive survey

research design according to Loeb, Dynarski, McFarland, Morris, Reardon, & Reber, (2017) allows for the collection and analysis of data to describe the characteristics of the population under study.

2.1.1 Ethics Statement

The Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria, approved this research project ethically. The research subjects provided their informed consent. Page | 384

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. Aba is known for its vibrant fashion industry, with numerous fashion designers operating across the area. The choice of Aba as the study area provides a diverse and representative sample of fashion designers, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability within the fashion industry.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for this study was 487, which comprises all registered fashion designers operating in Aba. This includes individuals involved in various aspects of fashion design, such as clothing, accessories, and footwear. The population is diverse, consisting of both established fashion designers and emerging entrepreneurs in the fashion industry. Hence, the total population was used for the study, as the population is manageable

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The title of the Questionnaire is: Questionnaire on Perceived Entrepreneurial Sustainability and Financial Stability among Fashion Designers (QPESFAFD) and was made up of 30 items. The questionnaire was made up of two parts. Part one which elicited information from the respondents on their demographic data, and Part two which was made up of three sections – section A B and C. Section A elicited information on the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State, Section B sought information on perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region and section C sought information on the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability. The questionnaire was developed based on a five – point response options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Data was distributed and collected through 5 trained research assistants who administer the questionnaires and collect responses from respondents. However 421 questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The collected data was analyzed using means, and standard deviations which answer the research questions. Decision on research questions were taken based on real limits of numbers. Thus, mean rating of 2.50 and above were considered as agreed, while items with mean rating below 2.50 were considered as disagreed.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: What are the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State?

Table 1: Mean responses and standard deviation on the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State

S/No	Items	\bar{X}	SD	R
1.	One engages in environmentally friendly production processes	3.12	1.11	A
2.	Waste reduction measures is a priority for fashion designers	2.78	1.6	A
3.	Local artisans and craftsmen enhances the sustainability of fashion businesses	3.49	1.2	A
4.	Fair trade practices contributes to the long-term sustainability of fashion businesses	2.62	1.09	A
5.	Staff training and development is essential for sustainable growth in the fashion industry	2.67	0.74	A
6.	Innovative technologies improves the sustainability of fashion businesses	2.51	1.03	A
7.	Strong online presence is important for the sustainability of fashion businesses	3.40	0.51	A
8.	Quality standards enhances the reputation and sustainability of fashion businesses	2.51	1.18	A
9.	Policies and support is a significant role in promoting sustainability among fashion designers	2.77	1.25	A
10.	Monitoring and evaluating environmental impact is a key aspect of sustainable fashion businesses	2.80	1.33	A

Key: \bar{X} = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation, N = number of respondent, A= Agree, D= Disagree, R= remark

Table 1 showed the mean responses of the respondents on perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State. The result revealed that all the 10 items had their mean values ranging from 2.51 to 3.49, which were above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents agreed that all the 10 items are the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State.

Table 2: How do these perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region? Page | 386

Table 2: Mean responses and standard deviation on the perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	R
1	Consumer perceptions of a fashion brand's reputation impact its financial stability	3.39	0.42	A
2	Brand image influences consumer spending habits within the fashion industry	2.59	0.36	A
3	Product quality affects the financial success of fashion businesses	3.20	0.57	A
4	Pricing strategies impact the financial stability of fashion businesses	2.51	0.28	A
5	Social media presence impacts the financial success of fashion businesses	3.64	1.11	A
6	Celebrity endorsements influence the financial stability of fashion brands	2.49	0.36	D
7	Customer reviews and word-of-mouth are in shaping perceptions of fashion brands' financial stability	3.27	1.25	A
8	Innovation and product differentiation contribute to the financial success of fashion businesses	3.24	1.21	A
9	Product availability and distribution channels impact the financial stability of fashion businesses	3.12	1.39	A
10	Fashion businesses' online presence affects their financial performance	2.40	0.41	A

Key: \bar{X} = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation, N = number of respondent, A= Agree, D= Disagree, R= remark

Table 2 showed the mean responses of the respondents on perceptions influencing the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region. The result revealed that all the 10 items had their mean values ranging from 2.40 to 3.64, which were above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents agreed that all the 10 items are the perceptions influencing the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region.

Table 3: What are the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability?

Table 3: Mean responses and standard deviation on the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	R
1	Ever-changing consumer preferences pose a challenge to sustaining your fashion business	3.60	1.24	A
2	Maintaining a balance between creativity and commercial viability is a significant challenge in the fashion industry	3.94	1.36	A

3	Access to funding and capital is a major obstacle for fashion designers in achieving financial stability	3.85	1.27	A
4	Maintaining a loyal customer base in the competitive fashion market	3.41	1.78	A
5	The lack of infrastructure and resources in the fashion industry	3.47	1.31	A
6	International expansion and entering new markets can contribute to the long-term financial stability	3.43	1.06	A
7	High operational costs, including production and marketing expenses, hinder the financial stability	3.87	1.35	A
8	Maintaining strong brand identity and reputation pose a challenge	3.20	1.43	A
9	Future prospects of my fashion business will create me achieving financial stability	3.02	1.21	A
10	Governmental regulations and policies have a significant impact on the financial stability	3.60	1.03	A

Key: \bar{X} = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation, N = number of respondent, A= Agree, D= Disagree, R= remark

Table 3 showed the mean responses of the respondents on key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability. The result revealed that all the 10 items had their mean values ranging from 3.02 to 3.94, which were above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents agreed that all the 10 items are the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability.

The findings of the study in table 1 revealed the perceived entrepreneurial sustainability strategies adopted by fashion designers in Abia State. Which includes: environmental friendly production processes, waste reduction measures, fair trade practices, staff training and development, strong online presence, quality standards and policies and support. These findings are in line with Olokundun et al. (2018) and Okpara and Wynn (2007) who revealed that fashion designers that put sustainable practices first typically have stronger financial results and are more resilient in volatile market conditions and Fischer, Brettel, & Mauer, 2020; Kamaludin, Xavier, & Amin, 2024, who stated there are other dimensions of entrepreneurial sustainability. These include economic sustainability, which is defined as the long-term financial stability and consistent profit-making potential of company activities.

The study in table 2, also identify the perceptions influence the financial stability of fashion businesses in the region. Some identify perceptions that influence the financial stability of fashion businesses includes: consumer perceptions product quality brand image pricing strategies social media presence customer reviews and word-of-mouth innovation and product differentiation product availability and distribution channels and fashion businesses' online. These findings can be used in line with Ruozi, Ferrari, Ruozi, & Ferrari, (2013); Wanjohi, (2013) and Aloqab, Alobaidi, & Raweh, (2018) who noted that risk management: Stability of finances depends on effective risk management. This entails determining, evaluating, and reducing a variety of risks, including as liquidity, credit, market, and operational risks. Adopting strong risk management procedures improves resilience to

external shocks and protects against unforeseen losses. Castellano & Dubovec, (2017); Claessens & Rojas-Suarez, (2016); and Anarfo & Abor, (2020) noted that Maintaining financial stability requires adherence to regulatory rules and procedures, especially for financial institutions. Respecting regulatory frameworks lowers the possibility of financial crises and systemic risks by fostering good governance, accountability, and transparency. Castells (2010) observed that Fashion 4.0 may be seen in the broader framework of a postindustrial fashion businesses, in which individuals are less bound by space and time and value experiences over material possessions. Also, Hunt's utopian (2005) Manifesto for Postindustrial Design, authoritative, centrally positioned designers are going extinct along with heavy mechanized mass manufacturing.

The study in table 3, highlight the key challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability. Some challenges and opportunities faced by fashion designers in sustaining their businesses and achieving financial stability includes: ever-changing consumer preferences, access to funding and capital, maintaining a loyal customer, lack of infrastructure and resources, high operational costs, maintaining strong brand identity and governmental regulations and policies. These findings can be used in line with Ihejirika & Ndu, (2018) who noted that access to sustainable materials, infrastructure, access to funding and capital, maintaining a loyal customer, lack of infrastructure and resources, high operational costs, maintaining strong brand identity and governmental regulations and policies, and market prospects are among the hurdles that local fashion designers in Abia State must overcome. Also, Sánchez, & Hartlieb, 2020; Yulistiyono, Andriani, & Rukmana, (2023) noted that to guarantee that their ideas are viable for mass production, designers must carefully combine their creative vision with financial feasibility. Isabel, Teixeira, Luis, & Silva, 2023; Ahsan, (2024) also noted that businesses which embrace sustainability are more likely to attract talent, investors, and customers who respect ethics and accountability.

4. Conclusion

Perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability are integral to the success and longevity of fashion businesses in Abia State. Fashion designers' perceptions of entrepreneurial sustainability in Abia State reflect a complex interplay of global trends, local traditions, and economic imperatives. Therefore, sustainability challenges in the fashion industry require a multifaceted approach that considers environmental, social, and economic dimensions that will address their needs. Thus, stakeholders in the fashion industries can collectively work towards building a more sustainable and resilient fashion ecosystem in Abia State. The integral relationship between perceived entrepreneurial sustainability and financial stability among fashion designers in Abia State can enhance financial performance, resilience, and competitiveness in the dynamic fashion industry landscape. There should be regular workshops and training sessions that will focus on financial management and planning specifically tailored for fashion designers. Networking and collaboration platforms should facilitate knowledge sharing, resource pooling, and collaboration among fashion designers in Abia State. Sustainable practices and ethical fashion principles among

fashion designers in Abia State should be promoted through education, awareness campaigns, and incentives in other to encourage designers to adopt environmentally friendly production processes, utilize sustainable materials, and embrace fair labor practices throughout their supply chains.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

DN, CAC, RAW, and MEU conceived and designed the research. DN, CAC, RAW and MEU developed the research design, collected and analysed the data, co-wrote the manuscript. All authors have approved the published version.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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